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НОВОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ В XXI ВЕКЕ

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взгляды

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И НОВОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ

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DIAGNOSIS, PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF HEMORRHOIDS IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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Annotation: *According to statistics, hemorrhoids are 5% more common in women who have given birth than in nulliparous women. This disease occurs in 7.7% of non-pregnant women, 25.7% of pregnant women and 49.8% of women who have given birth. Pregnancy and childbirth are the main factors that cause cystitis in women. This manifests itself in the form of constipation, uterine pressure on the intestinal walls and slowing of blood flow in the portal vein system. Treatment and prevention of hemorrhoids in pregnant women is one of the most urgent problems of modern coloproctology. Treatment of hemorrhoids in pregnant women is somewhat different from the treatment of this pathology in all other people. Any drug used by a pregnant woman, even for topical use, cannot be considered completely safe for the fetus, therefore, the drug should be used during pregnancy only if necessary, and the potential benefit of the drug clearly outweighs the possible harm to the fetus. mother and fetus. In most cases, hemorrhoids in pregnant women can be treated with conservative measures, in rare cases, there is a need for hemorrhoidectomy. Thus, emergency hemorrhoidectomy in pregnant women is 0.2%.*

Keywords: *hemorrhoids, pregnancy, diagnosis, prevention, treatment*

ДИАГНОСТИКА, ПРОФИЛАКТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕМОРРОЯ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ

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Аннотация: *По статистике, геморрой 5% чаще встречается у рожавших женщин, чем у нерожавших. Это заболевание встречается у 7,7% небеременных, 25,7% беременных и 49,8% родивших женщин. Беременность и роды являются основными факторами, вызывающими цистит у женщин. Это проявляется в виде запоров, давления матки на стенки кишечника и замедления кровотока в системе воротной вены. Лечение и профилактика геморроя у беременных – одна из актуальнейших проблем современной колопроктологии. Лечение геморроя у беременных несколько отличается от лечения этой патологии у всех остальных людей. Любой препарат, применяемый беременной, даже для местного применения, не может считаться полностью безопасным для плода, поэтому применять препарат при беременности следует только в случае необходимости и потенциальная польза от препарата явно превышает возможный вред для плода. мать и плод. В большинстве случаев геморрой у беременных поддается лечению консервативными мероприятиями, в редких случаях возникает необходимость*

геморроидэктомии. Так, экстренная геморроидэктомия у беременных составляет 0,2%.

Ключевые слова: *геморрой, беременность, диагностика, профилактика, лечение.*

A hemorrhoids is a pathological expansion of the veins of the rectum, which is manifested by periodic bleeding, internal nodes coming out of the back exit hole, and frequent inflammation. At its base, there are cavernous structures, internal and external nodes are distinguished [45]. Pregnancy and childbirth are the main factors that cause cystitis in women. This is manifested in the form of constipation, pressure of the uterus on the intestinal walls, and a decrease in blood flow in the portal vein system [53]. According to statistics, it is 5% more common in women who have given birth than women who have not given birth. This disease occurs in 7.7% of non-pregnant women, 25.7% of pregnant women, and 49.8% of women who have given birth [3].

Constipation is common in women during pregnancy. It usually lasts 3-5 weeks. It is very difficult for patients with Bavocil and affects the general condition of patients. The problem of hemorrhoids in women during pregnancy is one of the main problems of modern coloproctology. The problem is that during the growth of the fetus in the mother's womb, it puts pressure on the veins of the rectum, squeezing the blood vessels. This phenomenon is clearly observed in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy. This situation, in turn, causes complaints in the postpartum period in patients. In addition, the disease is acute and chronic. In many cases, the acute form of Bavosil's disease is caused by complications of the chronic form after thrombosis, bleeding and inflammation. According to scientific statistics, 50% to 80% of young mothers-to-be have problems with cystic fibrosis [10]. It is well known that during pregnancy, the treatment of hemorrhoids has its own characteristics and the drugs that have a local effect have a negative effect on the body of the pregnant mother and the fetus [32, 33].

Treatment and prevention of hemorrhoids in pregnant women is one of the most urgent problems of modern coloproctology [1, 18,22].

Pregnancy and childbirth, chronic constipation, the pressure of the uterus on the intestinal walls, the wrong position of the uterus, and dampness in the portal vein are important factors in the development of cysts in women [16,19].

As a result, the disease process can be acute and chronic. In fact, these forms are stages of the same process. In an acute condition, thrombosis develops in the nodes, accompanied by pain in the posterior discharge area. In some cases, acute inflammation is accompanied by swelling in the perianal area, necrosis of nodes. Thrombosis in lymph nodes is an indication for starting anticoagulant therapy under the supervision of a proctologist. Bleeding, which is usually repeated in the chronic course of the disease, is characterized by the fall of the lymph nodes during defecation [20].

Cystitis is the most common disease during pregnancy and the postpartum period. The disease is acute and chronic. It manifests itself in the form of thrombosis, inflammation and bleeding. The acute form is considered a complication of the chronic form [21].

Complications are divided into thrombosis and inflammation. This classification represents the pathogenesis of the disease, provides convenience and opportunity in practice. Depending on the stage of the disease and the severity of the disease, the clinical indicators are determined objectively, and the necessary treatment method is selected. Conservative treatment of acute and chronic cystitis prevents the appearance of symptoms of acute cystitis, the recurrence of complications, and the transition to chronic cystitis. In this, anti-inflammatory, pain-relieving, hemostatic drugs are used. They improve blood flow and normalize microcirculation in the cavernous tissue [19,22]. The first worst complication of the disease is bleeding from the anal canal [1]. In more than half of patients, this condition is reversed. Continuous bleeding from lymph nodes causes anemia in patients. Anorectal bleeding can be a symptom of colon cancer, diverticulosis, nonspecific ulcerative colitis, and granulomatous colitis [23]. The second most common symptom of hemorrhoids is this - is the descent of the nodes. In addition, polyps and colorectal cancer are also found under the guise of papilloma. When a cyst appears, it is necessary to conduct a thorough examination: finger examination, rectoscopy, colonoscopy or irrigoscopy. A biopsy is necessary when a tumor is suspected [24]. Pain syndrome is rare in chronic anal fissures and occurs with complications such as thrombosis with perianal edema in external anal fissures, anal canal rupture, internal anal fissures. The cause of pain syndrome is acute or chronic paraproctitis, rectal cancer with perfolcal inflammation, or complications around the anus. may be transient Crohn's disease. Mucus or pus discharge can be in inflammation of the rectum and tumor diseases. Inflammation of the anal canal can lead to acute paropractice, one of the serious complications of the disease, which is difficult to treat [6,10].

During pregnancy, clinical symptoms of hemorrhoids do not have a specific appearance. Most often, there is pain in the back area, rectal bleeding and anal itching. During the gestational period, the condition is often detected in the asymptomatic stage. These women do not have any complaints, but an anoscopic examination reveals a complication [4,25]. Timely detection of pregnant women with no clinical symptoms and preventive measures in them allows preventing the development of the process complicating the delivery and postpartum period [26].

It should be noted that the clinical manifestations of the disease in pregnant women are prolonged over time. At the beginning of the disease, there are unpleasant sensations in the anus, which increase after defecation [4,27]. Then the following symptoms appear: pain, enlargement of cystic nodes, bleeding, anal itching [7,9]. In half of the women who had hemorrhoids during pregnancy, after giving birth, the disease passes into the period of infection. When the fetus is large, in the second stage of labor, the parietal nodes are

mechanically compressed by the fetal head [28]. Violation of venous flow and tissue hypoxia ensure direct activation of arteriovenous anastomoses located in the cavernous space of the rectum. The longer the period of childbirth, the more clearly these processes are revealed [29]. After childbirth, the sphincter of the anus gradually shrinks, the internal nodes become smaller and straighten independently, but with a rapid contraction of the sphincter, the nodes can be compressed and an acute complication may develop [6,10]. Conservative treatment is carried out in the acute and initial stages of chronic inflammation. The goal of therapy is to relieve pain and inflammation, normalize blood circulation in the rectum [30].

Conservative treatment includes: systemic treatment with phlebotonics and anticoagulants, ointments, gels, suppositories and microclyses that improve wound healing, local treatment with analgesic and antipruritic drugs [31]. At the same time, a diet containing foods rich in fiber is prescribed: vegetables, fruits, flour products. Spicy foods, spices and alcohol should be excluded from the diet [6,7,52]. In the period of pregnancy and the postpartum period, budesonide has a significant impact not only on the patient's condition, but also on the quality of life. When choosing a drug for the treatment of a pregnant or lactating woman, we must consider the safety of the patient, as well as the fetus and newborn, and the final effect of the treatment [32,35]. In half of the women who had hemorrhoids during pregnancy, there is an outbreak of the disease after childbirth. According to a number of authors, more than 50% of pregnant women suffer from hemorrhoids, their number increased to 80% in the later period [5,34]. In the first trimester of pregnancy, the disease occurs in 33% of pregnant women, in the second trimester - in 35%, in the third trimester - in 42%, after childbirth - in 41%, and the frequency of the diagnosis increases significantly as the age of pregnant women increases [7]. It causes the disease to worsen after childbirth in women who have had hemorrhoids before giving birth. More than half of women who have had a miscarriage during pregnancy complain of severe postpartum illness [36,37].

Despite the fact that this problem has been well studied for a long time, there are certain difficulties in solving it, which is often associated with multidisciplinary pathology in medicine. Obstetricians and gynecologists refer pregnant women with cystic fibrosis to special specialists "send". Surgeons and coloproctologists, in turn, are "afraid" to treat hemorrhoids in pregnant women. Because in almost all indications for the treatment of cystitis, the use in pregnant women is not recommended or recommended with caution [4,11,38].

Pregnant women are a very vulnerable group with a high risk of developing complications. Therefore, it is very important to study the characteristics of the development of hemorrhoids in pregnant women. These factors reach their maximum level in the 3rd trimester of pregnancy [1 2].

The continuous and increasing compression of the pelvic vessels by the uterus plays a leading role in the rapid expansion of the rectal vessels. Current evidence suggests that

medical treatment with phlebotropic drugs, topical agents, and a high-fiber diet are the preferred strategies for treating early stage chronic vasculitis and acute vasculitis thrombosis [39]. Currently, most doctors do not recommend taking any medication during pregnancy, and attribute it to the negative effect on the fetus. In turn, many pregnant women seek to protect themselves from taking the drug for the same reasons [40]. Unfortunately, this practice also applies to drugs used during pregnancy, in particular, as phlebotonics. As a result of this approach, despite the many publications devoted to various aspects of hemorrhoids, many issues of prevention and treatment of hemorrhoids and its complications in pregnant women are still controversial [41]. The need for preventive measures, timely detection of the disease and medical treatment in pregnant women is important for ensuring a normal course of pregnancy and reducing the risk of postpartum complications. Additional research is being conducted to find optimal ways to manage pregnant women with ovarian cysts in order to develop recommendations for implementing a set of diagnostic and treatment measures in these women [5,15,42]. The "gold standard" of hemorrhoid treatment is hemorrhoidectomy, a surgical method that has been used since the middle of the 20th century [13]. In the USA and European countries, usually hemorrhoidectomy is currently performed only in 17-21% of patients, and the rest are treated with minimally invasive methods [16,17,43]. At the same time, in Russia, hemorrhoidectomy is the most common treatment method, which is performed in 75% of patients, and minimally invasive methods are used in only 3% of patients [9,22,25,26,44]. In order to reduce the risk and effectiveness of hemorrhoid treatment, minimally invasive outpatient treatment methods have been developed: sclerotherapy, latex ligation, infrared photocoagulation, suturing of hemorrhoidal arteries under the control of ultrasound dopplerometry [15].

In recent years, surgery as an independent method of treatment is used only in 20-25% of patients, and even then it is performed only in the late stages of the disease [8]. When choosing a method of treatment for hemorrhoids, it should be remembered that in the absence of normal anatomical conditions and clinical signs of the disease, one should not rush to surgical treatment. Conservative treatment plays a leading role in the early stages of acute and chronic disease [3, 14]. Their main purpose is to relieve pain and inflammation, normalize blood circulation in the rectum and regulate digestion. Conservative medical treatment can be general (drugs that increase vascular tone, improve blood flow through small vessels and cavernous veins) and local (wound healing, analgesic and antipyretic ointments, suppositories, microclysms and baths) [9, 15,46,52]. In addition, it is important to prevent the onset of the disease: fight with diarrhea, eat right, limit the use of spicy food and alcohol, observe defecation hygiene, prevent hypodynamia, etc. [47].

First of all, it is necessary to fight constipation and prevent constipation for a long time. A diet rich in fruits and vegetables can help with this. Patients with hemorrhoids are strictly prohibited from alcohol, salty, spicy food, because these products increase the blood filling of the pelvic veins and, first of all, blood filling in hemorrhoidal venous

entanglements [48]. Eating fatty foods slows down the digestion process and thus creates conditions for the development of constipation. It is recommended to limit the use of onions, mustard, black bread, legumes, unripe fruits and berries. Broccoli, corn, carrots, ripe apples, beets, cabbage, potatoes, raisins, apricots, dried apricots and honey are recommended [47,48,52]. Porridge, especially if eaten by grinding barley or oatmeal, also prevents constipation. If prone to constipation, the 3rd diet table is recommended. If prone to diarrhea, table 4b is recommended. In addition, it is advisable to use the following: regular consumption of enzyme preparations, substances affecting the flora and peristalsis of the small and large intestine, hydrophilic colloids or liquid; Plant and flax seeds are often used abroad. If you are prone to diarrhea, it is advisable to take adsorbents that improve absorption, enzyme and bacterial preparations, and substances that affect the peristalsis of the small and large intestines [1,49]. Increasing the strength of the muscles of the anal area and abdominal wall, reducing the dampness in the veins of the small groin area, physical therapy, hygienic gymnastics help to improve the function of the large intestine. It is also recommended to lie with the pelvis elevated for 15 minutes 2-3 times a day, for example, on a small pillow [9 11,50]. Hypothermia, especially in the lower part of the body, is very important not to sit on a cold surface, to avoid long (over 1 hour) walking and long standing or sitting work [51]. The use of personal hygiene products after each defecation has a good preventive effect. Washing with warm water, even cold water, can be continued for a short time (from 15-30 to 60 seconds) to wash the anal area with cold water [10, 14]. When choosing a drug for the treatment of a pregnant or lactating woman, it is necessary to consider its safety for the patient as well as for the fetus and newborn, which significantly limits the choice of the doctor [2]. The basis of the general treatment is the use of phlebotropic drugs that affect the increase in venous tone, the improvement of microcirculation in the cavernous bodies, and the normalization of blood flow in them [7, 11]. This group includes glyvenol, rutoside, cyclo-3 Forte, diosmin and ginkor forte. Heparin ointment, gincorprocto, Proctoglyvenol and Hepatrombin g are usually used as local thrombolytic and anti-inflammatory effects . The drug of choice for improving the regeneration of the anal canal and mucous membrane of the vagina is posterizan in the form of suppositories and ointments[1, 8, 10].

Women with asymptomatic cysts are prescribed only preventive measures. In the I-II stages of the disease, suppositories and ointments, syrups of medicinal herbs and oral medications are treated. Rectal suppositories containing analgesic components can be used after defecation. Oil suppositories can be placed in the spasm of the anus sphincter. If the cyst comes together with an anal fissure and acute cyst is treated conservatively in the hospital. It includes rest, nutrition, cleansing enemas, drugs normalizing intestinal activity, novocaine blockade in the anus, local treatment with suppositories and ointments. When removing internal nodes, without acute inflammatory phenomena, they are carefully performed on the nodes after defecation. (this is best done in a hot sitting bath). When there is an urge to defecate, small cleansing enemas are recommended. Women are

strictly prohibited from hard physical labor and some domestic work. At the time of onset of the disease, pregnant women who are affected by the disease are forced to go to the hospital and undergo surgical treatment. Terms of operation are determined separately. Patients with such complications are treated with surgery (hemorrhoidectomy) or minimally invasive treatment methods (small or bloodless operations). Such methods include sclerotherapy, rubber band ligation, infrared photocoagulation, and laser coagulation. If the condition of the pregnant woman is normal, all interventions are transferred to the postpartum period. Aggravation of the uterus, especially in combination with postpartum injuries, is the most common disease that affects the quality of the postpartum period. Both men and women suffer from hemorrhoids in the same way. One of the main factors in the development of cysts in women is pregnancy and childbirth. The treatment of hemorrhoids in pregnant women is slightly different from the treatment of this pathology in all other people. Any drug used by a pregnant woman, even for local use, cannot be considered completely safe for the fetus, therefore, the drug should be used during pregnancy only if it is necessary and the potential benefit of the drug clearly exceeds the possible harm to the mother and fetus.

In conclusion, in most cases, hemorrhoids in pregnant women can be treated with conservative means, and in rare cases there is a need for hemorrhoidectomy. Thus, emergency hemorrhoidectomy is 0.2% in pregnant women [12]. Treatment of hemorrhoids in pregnant women is dominated by local conservative treatment, diet and disease prevention methods. The most important conditions for the successful treatment and prevention of this disease are the normalization of the gastrointestinal tract, the regulation of the consistency of the intestinal contents and the transit of feces through the large intestine. For this purpose, a diet rich in plant fiber is recommended, with regular and adequate consumption of water and osmotically active nutrients such as fruit and vegetable juices. Of course, the most effective and safe medicines are always given, including those made from natural ingredients.

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